

THE IMPORTANCE OF RISK FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ISCHEMIC DISEASE AND DEATH

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ABSTRACT

The article analyses the yearly growing number of deaths from cardiovascular disease on the planet, the non-communicable diseases representing the main part of morbidity and premature deaths of including the ischemic heart disease, the morbidity from ischemic heart disease and the role of risk factors in the increase in death, the risk levels of different risk factors in the development of ischemic disease and death, separately and in combination.

Relevance. The role of risk factors in the increase in morbidity and mortality from coronary heart disease is significant. It is known from the literature that a number of generally accepted risk factors include; arterial hypertension, obesity, hyperlipidemia, diabetes mellitus, smoking, personality type, insufficient knowledge of people with coronary heart disease, low patient visits to the doctor and a specific objective examination of the cardiovascular system in patients without typical complaints of typical angina pectoris failure to enter is also included. [1, 2, 3, 4]. Many researchers point out that, in addition to individual risk factors, they are more important when combined [5, 6, 7, 8]. When various risk factors are added, It should be noted that the main part of morbidity and early death in the Republic are non-communicable diseases, especially coronary heart disease [10]. Perennial observations suggest an increase in

morbidity and mortality from coronary heart disease in different populations. According to the World Health Organization, the number of deaths from cardiovascular disease on earth has increased in the last 20 years, with 17.5 million people dying from cardiovascular disease each year, accounting for 31% of all deaths worldwide [11]. If deaths from cardiovascular disease continue to increase in this way, It is estimated that by 2030, almost 23.6 million people will die from cardiovascular disease, mainly heart disease and stroke.[12].

The above statistics show that ischemic heart disease is one of the most important medical-social and medical-economic problems of our time.

The purpose of the study. To study the importance of risk factors in the development of ischemic heart disease and death.

Materials and methods. An epidemiological survey of 1,814 men aged 20-69 in Yunusabad district of Tashkent was conducted. The study used classification and risk assessment methods recommended by the World Health Organization for population surveys. Socio-hygienic and sanitary-statistical methods were widely used in the analysis of materials collected during the study.

Conclusion and discussion. Initially, the development of ischemic heart disease was analyzed when the risk levels were different. According to the data obtained, when the risk level was very high, ischemic heart disease detected in the first study was the most recorded, accounting for 73.33% (Table 1).

Table 1.

Analysis of the development of ischemic heart disease in those with different levels of risk (in%).

Previously diagnosed and newly developed ischemic heart disease.				
Risk level	There was no and no ischemic heart disease	Detected at first inspection	Newly developed Ischemic heart disease	Total
Past (n = 4)	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00
Average (n = 36)	80.56	0.00	19.44	100.00
High (n = 14)	64.29	0.00	35.71	100.00
Very high (n = 15)	26.67	73.33	0	100.00
That's all	64.25	8.10	25.98	100.00

It should be noted that in the high-risk groups, the incidence of ischemic heart disease was the highest, at 35.71%. Slightly lower risk levels were reported (19.44%). Significantly, ischemic heart disease was not detected in those with low and very high risk levels. It can be seen that the development of ischemic heart disease in the very high-risk group was the most recorded in the primary examination, accounting for 73.33%. The reason that newly developed cardiac ischemic disease was not detected during the re-examination is that we can assume that patients with a very high risk did not survive until re-examination.

In order to study the relationship between the number of risk factors and the development of ischemic heart disease, a

previous study analyzed the detection and newly developed cases of coronary heart disease when the number of risk factors varied. The results showed that with an increase in the number of risk factors, a significant increase in the number of ischemic heart diseases detected in the primary examination was noted (Table 2). It should be noted that ischemic heart disease is most commonly detected when three (17.86%) and four (20.0%) risk factors are combined.

among individuals whose number of risk factors varied in the primary examination.

Detection of ischemic heart disease and analysis of newly developed cases (in%)

Previous and newly developed ischemic heart disease.				
Number of risk factors	There was no and no ischemic heart disease	Detected at the initial inspection	Newly developed Ischemic heart disease	Total
Risk factor 1 (n = 156)	66.67	8.33	25.00	100.00
Risk factor 2 (n = 90)	61.11	15.55 *	23.33	100.00
Risk factor 3 (n = 28)	60.00	17.86 *	22.14	100.00
Risk factor 4 (n = 5)	60.00	20.00 *	20.00	100.00

Note: The level of reliability for a single risk factor is indicated (* - p < 0.05).

It should be noted that the incidence of newly developed ischemic heart disease among individuals with a different number of risk factors was somewhat different. That is, newly developed coronary heart disease was observed the least (20.0%) when four risk factors were added, and more when it was three (22.14%), two (23.33%), and one (25.0%) factors. ischemic heart disease was noted. From the data presented, it can be concluded that with the increase in the number of risk factors, a decrease in the development of new cases of ischemic heart disease was observed.

In order to study the importance of risk factors in deaths from coronary heart disease, deaths from coronary heart disease and arterial hypertension among individuals with different levels of risk were analyzed. From the data obtained, it was found that deaths from ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension also increase with increasing risk (Table 3). It should be noted that the number of deaths from coronary heart disease and hypertension was higher at high (14.29%) and very high (28.32%) risk levels compared to low and moderate (6.98%) risk levels. Significantly, no deaths from coronary heart disease and arterial hypertension were observed among low-risk individuals.

Table 3.

Analysis of deaths from coronary heart disease and arterial hypertension among individuals with varying levels of risk (in%).

Risk level	Cause of death			
	Ischemic heart disease and AG	Other reasons	They are alive	Total
Past (n = 20)	0.00	5.00	95.00	100.00
Average (n = 140)	6.98 *	10.45	83.58	100.00
High (n = 67)	14.29 *	7.14	78.57	100.00

Very high (n = 113)	28.32 *	14.16	57.52	100.00
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Note: The reliability level compared to the previous group is indicated (* - $p < 0.05$).

As noted earlier, when various risk factors are combined, there is a significant increase in the risk of developing ischemic heart disease and the mortality associated with this disease [13]. Based on the above statistics and the results of a private research analysis, it can be said that there is a correlation between the level of risk and death from ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension. An increase in the number of deaths from ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension was observed with increasing risk.

Conclusions:

1. Risk factors played an important role in the development of ischemic heart disease, with the development of new ischemic heart disease being the highest recorded in high-risk groups, accounting for 35.71%.

2. As the number of risk factors increases, the risk of developing ischemic heart disease also increases, with the combination of three and four risk factors accounting for 17.86% and 20.0%, respectively.

3. An increase in mortality was observed with increasing risk, and deaths from ischemic heart disease and arterial hypertension were 6.98%, 14.29 %, and 28.32%, respectively, when the risk was moderate, high, and very high.

4. In order to carry out primary and secondary prevention of ischemic heart disease, it is necessary to correct them in the presence of various risk factors.

5. In order to prevent the development of new cases of ischemic heart disease and deaths from this disease, it is necessary to conduct ECG examinations in all individuals with risk factors.

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